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The Role Of Civic Education In Developing Leadership Quality Among Junior Secondary School Students In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This research examined the role of civic education in promoting good leadership. Leadership problems have been the major reason for underdevelopment in Nigeria. This study provided elucidation of concepts of civic education and leadership, problems faced by civic education, investigated the relationship between civic education and leadership, the impact of civic education on leadership traits, and the role of civic education in promoting good leadership. The research revealed that the leadership crises at different strata and levels of government are a function of the problems that have to do with civic education in schools; in the areas of content and context, lack of democratic school administration, lack of civil society's engagement, and lack of role model teachers. It contended that civic education is the only solution to varying leadership challenges, especially in Nigeria. The researcher recommended, among others, conscious efforts to inculcate in young students/children the value of civic responsibilities such as prudence, responsibility, and accountability. More academically qualified teachers should be employed to teach civic education which breeds good leadership at the various levels of government in Nigeria.

Keywords: Civic Education, Leadership, and curriculum

INTRODUCTION

Education is the most important instrument needed for the transformation of individual members of society to contribute meaningfully to their personal development and to the development of that society. The federal government of Nigeria in the NPE (2009) declared that education is an excellent instrument for achieving national development. Civic education is the continual and systematic provision of

information and learning experiences to all citizens for their effective participation in democratic life. It studies the rights, responsibilities, and roles of citizens in a society, particularly within the democratic framework. It also aims to equip individuals with the knowledge, skills needed to fully participate in activities that have to do with civic and political life. Civic education is the vehicle for the inevitable transfer of leadership facilities. Leadership dexterity proceeds from civic education, which makes for good governance. The dividends of good governance bring about a habitable society, a society devoid of crises but characterized by peace and tranquility, orderliness and decency, and their attendant socio-economic development.

The curriculum of civic education consists of those areas of knowledge that have to do with the civic responsibility of citizens in society. It includes aspects of the moral development of the individual. Civic education is supposed to provide the necessary conditions for leadership among students to perform effectively in the position of leadership. The question here is whether civic education at the junior secondary school level provides those logical conditions for effective leadership in Nigeria is the issue.

Leadership is a concept that has universal significance; every organization, association, or group evolves under a concrete leadership structure. Olusuyi (2002) defines leadership as the ability to inspire, direct, motivate, and encourage others positively to a targeted end. Looking at the underdevelopment experienced in Nigeria today, Ighalo (1996) opined that bad leadership has largely been the bane of Nigerian society. It could be implied from the point of view of Igholola that leadership in Nigeria lacks integrity, accountability, and morality.

Education is the most vital tool for effective leadership, which is why one of the great educational thinkers, Plato, emphasized the role of education toward effective leadership. It is because of the inadequate leadership skills in various institutions of government that the indices of corruption, kidnapping, terrorism, and underdevelopment, among others, are found in Nigeria. It is on this basis that the researcher intends to analyze the role of civic education toward the development of leadership quality among junior secondary school students in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Generally, education is expected to expose individuals to all aspects of life that will make them effective members of society and quality leaders. Civic education, in particular, is one of the subject areas that is being introduced to train students to be good citizens and follow all the civic responsibilities in society, including quality and effective leadership. The FRN (2009) stated that one of the national educational goals is the development of an individual into a morally sound, patriotic, and effective citizen.

Recent research has shown that there are still cases of leadership failure and a diminishing economy in Nigeria. This is because leaders who are occupying various leadership positions are not exposed to the logical conditions necessary for leadership, which they are supposed to acquire right from school in those subject areas that have to do with humanities, civic education, and inclusive.

Leadership in Nigeria has suffered a great setback as a result of inappropriate leadership education at the various levels of our educational institutions. This lack of leadership education among our leaders resulted in a lack of accountability/responsibility, justice, and patriotism among others. Leaders are self-centered, it brought about instability of government policy and underdevelopment in all aspects of the Nigerian economy. It also manifested itself in the current insecurity in Nigeria. This is what motivated the researcher to look at the role of civic education toward the development of leadership qualities among junior secondary school students in Nigeria.

Concepts of Civic Education and Leadership

The concept of Civic Education comprises two important components — “Civic” and “Education”. Noah (2005) defines the term Civic as “the study of rights and duties of citizens and how government works.” On the other hand, Education means “a process of teaching, training, and learning, especially in schools and colleges, to improve knowledge and develop skills” (Hornby, 2006). Civic Education, therefore, is the process of studying how people can become good, disciplined, effective, and quality citizens in society. It is a kind of education that provides students with a rich knowledge and understanding of their

responsibilities as citizens. Civic education is a vital aspect of education that cultivates in citizens the sense of participating in the public life of a government and democracy, to use their rights and to discharge their responsibilities with the necessary knowledge and skills. Edward (2011) argued that civic education means “all the processes that affect people’s beliefs, commitments, capabilities and actions as members or prospective members of communities”. Civic education, thus, is not only acquired through formal education but also via informal education and other forms of socialization; its primary essence being to produce quality future citizenship that would participate in group decision making, negotiation, and social life of positive consequence. In a democracy, civic education is education in self-government. Self-government.

Problems faced by civic Education

Despite the contributions of civic education in building and creating good-behaved citizens who are active and participatory in the affairs of the societies, it still faces a lot of challenges, which have limited the effective and adequate realization of its purposes at secondary levels of the Nigerian education system.

Some of these problems are highlighted as follows:

1. **Content and context-related problem:** The contents of civic education have some deformity. The subject places great emphasis on the domestic 154 legal frameworks (Baye, 2016). In this vein, Tesfaye et al (2013) argued in the *Journal of Research in Adult and Continuing Education* that the lessons devote much time to inform students about the constitution, laws of the land, and policies of the government, while international laws and issues that have to do with leadership and good governance are being neglected.
2. **Lack of civil societies' engagement:** Educating Civic and Ethical Education by government alone will not be sufficient to create good citizens equipped with ethical values and good leadership culture, instead, it should also be corroborated by the teachings of other stakeholders such as the family, religious institutions, civil society organizations, the media and other institutions (Mulugeta, 2015). In this regard, the role of civil societies will not be underestimated in line with the position of the European Union (2011) that the role of civil societies in promoting good governance by engaging in Civic Education activities is well-known across the world.
3. **Lack of democratic school administration:** It is not uncommon to find an authoritarian tendency in Nigerian schools' administration. School principals are stakeholders in the implementation of the Civic Education curriculum. As the bedrock of implementing Civic Education, they should exhibit democratic activities and behaviour since they play a great role in shaping students' behaviour negatively or positively.
4. **Improper mode of delivery:** Improper mode of delivery of Civic and Ethical Education is hampering the effort of building good behaviour and creating active and participating citizens who can play a role in the democratization process of the country (Baye, 2016). Regarding this, Tesfaye et al (2013) opined that using plasma as a method of delivery is affecting learners from acquiring the required knowledge and skill from the subject. This problem is prevalent at the primary and secondary school levels, where plasma is being employed. The method does not appropriately fit the very nature of the subject because it involves frequent repetition, interaction, and participatory learning (Browne, 2013). It could be implied from the point of view of Browne that participatory and interactive methods such as role playing, problem-solving activities, and mock political or judicial activities are best received and appear to deliver better and long-term results. The fact that plasma 156 *Journal of Research in Adult and Continuing Education* is too fast, beamed only once, highly dependent on an uninterrupted flow of electric power, and in English with no local language support.
5. **External environment:** The behaviour of students is not formed exclusively from within a school. The influence of their peers, neighbours, families, and society as a whole plays a significant role. Peers are important socialization agents that greatly determine the decisions, attitudes, and behaviours of students (Korir et al, 2014). Students whose friends are involved in harmful activities, such as the intake of drugs and truancy, are likely to have a lower academic

performance. Though students are taught the good traits of a citizen, such as tolerance, honesty, civic mindedness, and compassion, their relationship with corrupted persons like smokers and drug addicts is affecting the traits they have learnt. Therefore, the whole external environment needs to be enabling to realize the goals of Civic Education more effectively. Weak democracy: UNDP (Baye, 2016) asserts that the paramount role should be played by the government for Civic Education to meet its goals. It could be implied by Baye that it is important that government is seen not just as one of several potential partners but as the pivotal actor, the 157 Journal of Research in Adult and Continuing Education disposition of which will have a major impact on the ability of Civic Education programmes to function and produce results. The author also opined that the government should make sure that necessary rights of assembly, expression, association, and others are recognized and protected; active interests from a variety of stakeholders, particularly civil society, are duly considered, and that resources to enable longer-term Civic Education initiatives to be undertaken should be provided. These conditions of Civic Education are better satisfied in a state having a democratic government. For citizens to be practically involved in the process of democracy in their country based on the knowledge they possess, the political environment should be participatory in the sense of allowing different stakeholders to take part in political decision-making. This is not the case in Nigeria. Therefore, Civic Education will continue to play a limited role in national development and cohesion.

6. **Lack of role model teachers:** The quality of teachers is important and has been globally accepted to be significantly associated with the quality of education in general and students' learning outcomes in particular. Thus, to transmit better knowledge and help to develop students' understanding, attitudes, skills, learning, and core values, teachers should have the competence in themselves as role models for their students who consciously or subconsciously learn their behaviour. However, it is common to see unmotivated Nigerian teachers with low morale due to poor salaries, low respect for and status of teachers and, poor school management and 158 Journal of Research in Adult and Continuing Education leadership. This negatively affects the proper role that teachers should play in delivering quality education and building good character in future adults for national development and cohesion. Conclusion: It is an undeniable fact that democratic governance is a crucial element for a nation

Relationship between Civic Education and Leadership

The interest and concern about character education and education for citizenship are not new in curriculum development in many countries of the world, especially in African countries. The two have always gone together. In Nigeria, the basic reason for establishing and expanding public schooling was to foster those traits of public and private character among students as a requirement for self-government. That was the reason for the earlier introduction of Civic Education in Nigeria's educational system in the 1950s-1970s and an emphatic reintroduction as a compulsory subject for primary and secondary schools in 2005. The objectives of civic education, among others, as expounded by Onwumere (2012) are to: Prepare the younger ones for good leadership and followership; inculcate in the students the values, cultures, ideas, ethics, knowledge... which help them live as one despite... differences; inculcate in the students the sense of patriotism, statesmanship, philanthropy, tolerance and other national ethics and values.... Character and civic virtue are important public matters needed for leadership at any level. They are primarily acquired via civic education. Essentially, schools —primary, secondary, and tertiary— were and are still expected to induce pupils, students, and undergraduates to act virtuously. Acting virtuously means more specifically that one should act with due restraint over his/ impulses, due regard for the rights and opinions of others, and reasonable concern for the probable and the long-term consequences of one's actions. This is the hallmark of leadership. The fact is that the culture of a given school and the classroom exerts powerful influences on what students learn about authority, responsibility, justice, civility, and respect.

The dynamic by which individuals acquire desired traits of private and public character is through exposure to an attractive model of behaviour enshrined in the objectives of civic education. Achebe's and Ignacimuthu's definitions of leadership as setting examples are espoused by Coles (1997) as he described the dynamic of character acquisition: Character is ultimately who we are expressed in our action, in how we live, in what we do – and so the children around us know, they absorb and take stock of what they observe, namely us – we adults living and doing in a certain spirit, getting on with one another in our various ways. Our children add up, imitate, file away what they have observed, and so very often later fall in line with particular moral counsel we unwittingly or quite oneself-consciously have offered them.... Character, especially that of a leadership trait, does not come pre-packaged. Character formation is a lengthy and complex process streamlined in civic education. Although Wilson (1991) asserted that “we do not know how character is formed in any scientifically rigorous sense”, yet, research and observations have shown that the study of traditional secondary school subjects such as literature, government, civic education, and history, when properly taught, provides the necessary framework for character education. More importantly, the aforementioned traditional school subjects provide a context for considering the traits of public and private character, which are vital to leadership as well as essential to the maintenance and improvement of a democratic way of life. The practice of leadership has enormous implications for the relationship between leadership and citizenship. In democracies, leadership is best understood as a dimension of citizenship itself, distinctive only in that it involves special competencies. The inseparability of civic education from leadership is further seen in its impact.

The role of civic education in promoting leadership quality

The curriculum content of civic education includes a body of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values that students are exposed to through their learning experiences. This can take place inside or outside the school, and it also involves interaction between students and the environment. Civic education covers topics like the history of democracy, how laws are made, and how citizens can participate in government. It involves three components: knowledge, values, and behaviours. Agu (2009) opined that the drive towards reengineering the process of teaching and learning civic education in our schools has become very imperative, especially in the face of a dwindling level of national consciousness and patriotic zeal. The line of thinking that the only source of leadership skills and ability is through natural endowment has been argued by many researchers. Recent research indicates that effective leadership is a result of both inherent traits and careful development of skills. In line with this, Rose Bach (2003) asserts that individuals should strive to focus on improving their leadership skills and which can be achieved through civic education.

The active leadership skills must begin at the very beginning of studentship and persist throughout education. Through civic education, even the smallest of students can learn how to work in teams or small communities, combine knowledge, share views, and create action plans appropriate to their level of development. They can also develop their ability to ask insightful questions, listen intently, and resolve disputes through negotiation and agreement. Civic education in a democratic country is unquestionably focused on fostering an appreciation for democratic standards and a thoughtful adherence to their standards and tenets, which are essential for effective leadership and government. Civic education plays a part in helping students realize that democratization is not an ideal system, and it is especially essential in removing indifferent and retreat inclinations from political life. The creation of a knowledgeable, useful, and accountable community is civic education's main goal (Bennis & Nanus, 1985). Citizens of Nigeria with the required information, abilities, and attitudes keep and participate strongly in democratic activities.

A free and open society cannot prosper without the above-mentioned factors, and the citizens' considerate obedience to the core ideas and the ideas of freedom. (Bennis & Nanus, 1985). Opined that a typical voter wants a community and an administration where people voluntarily carry out their duties, civil liberties are fortunate, individual worth and integrity are recognized, and the rule of law is upheld. All of these are provided by civic education, Human rights and duties, regard for the common welfare, the legal

system, fairness, equity, variety, truth, loyalty, autonomy, and the division of authorities are all part of the democratic society (Ajero, 2014). Intellectual skills are the result of being aware of all of these and making a concentrated attempt to put them into practice. Factually, the substance of social and political knowledge cannot be separated. Therefore, to think analytically about a governmental problem and address it head-on, for example, one needs to comprehend the present problem, its past, and its significance today. It could be implied from the point of view of Ajero that individuals need to identify their duties as a member of a particular society and their democratic duties as a citizen, which can only be achieved through education.

CONCLUSION

Civic education and leadership are indeed integral. Their connection and intricate connectivity, if genuinely explored, would guarantee good leadership. Good leadership has been the clamour of Nigeria. Junior secondary school is the first step to ensuring the inculcation of the right attitude for effective leadership training among students. Besides the introduction of civic education, there is a need for the schools to double their effort in ensuring that teachers of the subject teach the students well. This will enable Nigeria to achieve its goal of training accountable and responsible leaders who will take the country to greater heights.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Schools should inculcate leadership qualities such as prudence, responsibility, and accountability among students of junior secondary schools.
2. There should be a national initiative to revitalize civic education in schools to make it more utilitarian.
3. The national initiative championed by the federal government should focus on the importance of civic education for every child, which will provide a grounding in the rights and responsibilities of citizens.
4. More academically qualified, patriotic, and dedicated educators should be employed to handle civic education as a subject in the junior secondary schools.
5. The importance, role, and impact of civic education on leadership should always be communicated to students.
6. Federal and state legislatures, the board of education, and schools should reexamine the formal curricula of civic education and their assessment practices to determine the adequacy and effectiveness of their education programmes.

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